

Eri Silk and Bodo Weaving: Sustainable Innovation through Design Diversification for Contemporary Fashion

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Abstract

Eri silk, also known as Ahimsa silk, is eco-friendly, sustainable, and known for its ethical production. For centuries, the traditional handwoven textiles of the Bodo community have been known for their intricacy and cultural significance. However, these textiles are now facing a gradual decline due to a shortage of artisans, limited material for innovation, and limited market access, where there is a gap between traditional craftsmanship and contemporary consumer demand. At the same time, Bodoland is a significant hub for Eri cultivation, an opportunity to revitalise contemporary weaving through integration with a sustainable material. This study explores the integration of Eri silk with traditional Bodo weaving motifs by enhancing them through natural dye.

Through in-depth analysis by working with the artisans to understand their challenges, this study highlights how sustainable weaving practices can create opportunities in both cultural and economic aspects, extraction of using sustainable materials to enhance the aesthetic appearance, durability, and marketability. By bridging the gap between heritage weaving and contemporary demand, this study proposes a scalable model for textile sustainability and artisan empowerment.

More than just a fabric, weaving for the Bodo people is a living heritage, where weaving tales are created with tradition and identity. Yet, as modernisation accelerates and challenges multiply. The integration of Bodoland's ethically produced Eri silk, blended with the natural dye technique, can bridge the gap between tradition and contemporary sustainability. This study is not only about reviving the Bodo's textiles but also about empowering the artisans, creating a sustainable livelihood, and establishing it as a globally recognised craft. This study serves as a stepping stone for policymakers, designers, and researchers to build a more resilient, innovative, globally relevant ecosystem for the weaves of Bodoland, ensuring its preservation and evolution for future generations.

Keywords

Eri Silk, Sustainable Textiles, Weaver Empowerment, Natural Dyeing, Bodo Traditional Weaving.

Introduction

The Bodo community is the indigenous community of the Bodoland territorial region (BTR), which has a rich legacy of craftsmanship for generations and is especially known for its intricate, colourful, and vibrant textiles. The origin of their weaving has played a significant role in the cultural history of the Bodoland Territorial Region. It has been serving both as a form of artistic expression and a marker of social and cultural belonging.

Bodoland Territorial Region is an autonomous division of Assam, which came into existence in 2009 under the peace agreement, and the autonomy was signed in the year 2020. It is governed by the Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC) government and includes Baksa, Kokrajhar, Chirang, and Udalguri. The region is located on the north bank of the Brahmaputra, beneath the foothills of Bhutan and Arunachal Pradesh, and is predominantly inhabited by Bodo people and other indigenous communities of Assam.

The weaving tradition of the Bodo community is distinguished by intricate geometric patterns inspired by nature, each carrying deep meanings and stories. These pattern carries deep meanings and stories. These textiles were traditionally woven by women for both functional and ceremonial purposes. Despite their artistic and cultural value, the traditional weaving practices are increasingly threatened by modernisation, limited product innovation, and

shrinking market opportunities. There is also a noticeable decline in interest among the younger generation in pursuing this craft.

Eri Silk, also known as Ahimsa silk, is a natural, cruelty-free fibre indigenous to Assam. It offers an ideal material for sustainable fashion innovation. Its thermal properties, biodegradability, and cultural relevance make it highly suitable for integrating traditional craft into contemporary sustainable fashion. Currently, the global fashion industry is witnessing a shift towards sustainability, ethical production, and cultural authenticity, opening new avenues for indigenous craft.

Although weaving is practised throughout the Bodoland Territorial Region, this study is specifically on the Kokrajhar district. It is recognised as a historical and active hub for weaving practices, with a well-established network of women artisans skilled in traditional handloom techniques and actively engaged in Eri silk rearing and processing. This paper explores design diversification and sustainable innovation using Eri silk to revitalise the Bodo weaving tradition in Kokrajhar. The goal is to preserve cultural heritage while enhancing the economic well-being of rural women artisans by integrating traditional craftsmanship with contemporary market demands. It also aims to empower rural women artisans to participate in the contemporary fashion market through the creation of innovative, eco-friendly textile products.

Objective of study

The objective of this study is –

1. To document and analyse the traditional motifs, techniques, and cultural significances of Bodo textiles.
2. To explore the integration of Assam's sustainable material, Eri silk, and also evaluate their aesthetic and functional potential.
3. To develop contemporary products with the textiles of the Bodo community through a collaborative engagement with the rural weavers.
4. To experiment with natural dye on Eri silk and evaluate its aesthetic and functional potential.

Review of Literature

The weaving tradition of the Bodo is deeply embedded; it is not merely a craft but a cultural way of expressing their identity, history, and community knowledge, primarily by women artisans. Basumatary and Khawazawl (2024) emphasised that Bodo weaving is not merely a utilitarian craft but a cultural legacy that reflects the community's connection with nature, folklore, and spiritual belief. The geometric motifs, found in the textiles of Bodo, are more storytelling, symbolic than decorative.

Despite being a culturally rich, modern influence and limited economic opportunities have placed traditional weaving under threat. Brahma (2024) highlighted the gradual erosion of these practices due to declining artisan participation, lack of innovation, and shrinking local markets. The younger generation is increasingly disengaging from the craft, highlighting an urgent need for design-led intervention.

Design intervention plays a pivotal role in sustaining the intricate craft. Bahl (2024) explores in the study how a collaborative approach of integrating traditional crafts and contemporary design can rejuvenate the intricate local textiles. On the other hand, Kapur and Mittar (2014) argue that the culturally sensitive design inputs not only improve the aesthetics of the product but also enhance market relevance and artisan empowerment.

Parallely, sustainable indigenous material of Assam Eri silk has been gaining attention and aligns with the global shift of allocating towards sustainable fashion. Hani and Das (2019) have highlighted the evolution of Eri culture from a traditional livelihood to a potential driver of innovation in the sustainable textile segment. Eri silk's ethical production and thermal qualities make it fit for the contemporary fashion demand.

Natural dyeing has been a practice done for ages; now, with this, it has turned into a value addition, offering both aesthetic appeal and eco-friendliness. The study of the paper by Mochahary and Chennattuserry (2024) draws attention to the potential of the indigenous knowledge system, which includes the natural dye sources, resulting in a result creation of a unique, eco-friendly product. When Eri silk is woven with the Bodo motif, it will include natural dyes, and as a result, it will contribute to both cultural and environmental sustainability.

Research Question

1. What design-led strategies can enable rural Bodo women artisans to participate in co- creation processes that align traditional knowledge with contemporary fashion systems, while preserving their cultural identity?
2. How can natural dyeing techniques and contemporary design diversification enhance the aesthetic, functional, and market value of Bodo textiles?

3. In what ways can a locally sourced, sustainable fibre – Eri silk be meaningfully integrated with traditional Bodo motifs to address both environmental and cultural sustainability?

Methodology

This study follows a practice-based and observational textile design methodology, rooted in direct engagement with the Bodo artisans of Kokrajhar, Assam. The approach is overall a blend of field immersion, co-creation, experiments with material, and documentation on exploring design diversification with Eri silk can revive and sustain the intricacy of Bodo weaving.

A preliminary field study was conducted in 2022 with the community over several months. This stay allowed for a deep observation of the traditional weaving processes, daily routines, and their cultural significances surrounding the craftsmanship. Through participant observation, the weaving process, tools, and motifs were studied over direct and informal participation.

While during the previous study, a few interventions was done with cotton, the current study proposes the use of the most famous locally sourced Eri silk, which has not been experimented with. The use of this silk is proposed due to its eco-friendly properties, ethical production process, and cultural resonance in Assam; it is identified as a strategic material choice for linking tradition as well as sustainability.

The next phase of the study will involve the natural dyeing trials of Eri silk yarns, using locally available material from nature. A few of the weavers have experimented previously with natural dye, but with time, they have stopped doing it. The trial will be done with materials such as onion peel, turmeric, tea leaves, etc. The evaluation will assess –

1. Dye absorption and fastness on Eri silk
2. Compatibility of natural dyes and Bodo motifs.
3. Potential for market-friendly colour palettes from natural dyes

After which, the design development process will begin based on the observation and motif references, and a series of design prototypes will be proposed using the Bodo motif in various modified compositions, scaled for fashion and lifestyle products. The process will be done on Eri silk using a traditional loom, later on jacquard looms. The product categories will include scarves, home décor items, and fashion accessories that balance traditional symbolism and contemporary utility.

The final phase will end with documentation and future evaluation systematically with the planned outcomes of dyeing trials, motif adaptation, and prototype samples. Each product needs to be documented with steps in the form of a photograph. Later feedback will be taken from the artisans, collaborators, and potential users. On the completion of the experiments, the results will be analysed to assess the feasibility of the integration of sustainable materials and diversified design strategies in Bodo traditional weaving.

Figure 1 Eri Cocoon

Figure 2 Eri yarn

Figure 3 Eri Stole weaving in the Kokrajhar loom

Figure 4 Previous field experiments at Kokrajhar

Figure 5 Product intervention in cotton for domestic market

Figure 6 Experimentation during previous field study

Figure 7 Products prototypes For international market

Result and Discussion

The insights from field observation in Kokrajhar

The initial field visit was conducted in Kokrajhar, which reflected the intricacy of the weaving, how it is deeply rooted in the cultural practices of the women weavers. Field observations have revealed that weaving functions not only as a part of their livelihood, but also as a storytelling of their craftsmanship and as a cultural identity. Various motifs were identified with the local names and documented, such as hajw agor, which means the designs of hills, phul mawbla, which means varieties of bloomed flowers, and phareo megor, which depicts the pigeon eye, and many more. However, many other motifs were discovered that are confined to traditional products made by previous generations, and artisans now rarely explore diversified formats due to a lack of exposure.

Gap in material usage and artisan practice

Bodo weavers are highly skilled weavers with technical skills and traditional knowledge, but there is no integration seen with sustainable materials like Eri silk, as it has been said that these products are expensive and the local customers do not tend to buy much of it. Prior experiments with natural dyes have declined over time due to limited awareness, training, and a lack of understanding of the market demand. Artisanal feedback has found that few of them were interested, but due to proper training, material availability, and market connections, it could not take its shape.

The next phase of this study will involve the application of natural dye in the yarn stage on Eri, on which motif will be lifted with traditional Bodo motif, which, as a result, will offer a meaningful path to a sustainable revival of the craft. It is foreseen that the Eri silk will exhibit an expectational compatibility with the sources of natural dye and with traditional looms. The outcome is expected to reflect the cultural relevance while appealing to contemporary fashion and lifestyle markets.

Role of Design-led innovation in sustainable craft revival

The initial findings have suggested that when sustainable material like Eri silk is combined with Bodo motifs and natural dye, it can offer a meaningful path for the sustainable revival of the craft. But just with new material and methods, it won't be enough. To make this innovation a successful model, the involvement of the artisans must be from the beginning, not just as workers, but rather as co-creators. The artisan should brush up on training on natural dyes, new product development ideation with Eri silk. The product just needs to be able to get space in the market, such as exhibitions or a retail format. This needs to be done so that the product reach is wider with the right audience, and the artisans would be able to scale up their financial status than before to live a sustainable livelihood. The designs that will be planned to develop, such as scarves, home décor, etc., which meant to prove that it is possible to create a product that can celebrate local identity by using local motifs and culture. The designs that will be developed using Eri silk and natural dyes should match up and be useful for modern utility or modern fashion, or modern home settings, so that they can cater to the market around the globe. Further, if this model works out, it can be replicated in other craft forms.

Conclusion

Reviving Bodo traditional weaving through sustainable innovation and design diversification offers a meaningful pathway to bridge a cultural heritage with the contemporary fashion demand. By focusing on the sustainable material -Eri silk, a naturally sustainable fiber which will empower the artisans who, as a result will boast this incredible craftsmanship This study highlights the possibilities through a design-led approach to the sustainable revival of the Bodo weaving by exploring the integration of Eri

silk, natural dyeing techniques, and the traditional Bodo motifs, also reveals that that by introducing a diversified product which are culturally rooted can open new market opportunities, by combining with strategic branding and promoting digitally. This model of designed intervention will ultimately ensure that the weavers of the region become stakeholders in more of a sustainable fashion environment. This will give life to the fading craft with revitalisation to this intricate craftsmanship.

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